

ON AN APPARENTLY TRIBASIC ACID CHARACTER OF HYDROGEN MICA

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The lattice-structure of muscovite is well known mainly through the work of Jackson and West (*Z. Kristallog.*, 1931, 79, 2). On comminution, the weak K-O bonds of the lattice readily break giving platelets with K ions exposed on *a-b* planes. Finely ground muscovite was leached with dilute HCl to obtain hydrogen- or, acid-mica by the replacement of the exposed potassiums by hydrogen ions. Aqueous suspensions of this hydrogen mica were found to behave as weak tribasic acids judged from their potentiometric titration curves with NaOH and KOH. The first inflexion in the titration curve, which is often very weak, occurs near about p_H 7.0. The other two inflexions are much more prominent and they are located at about p_H 9.0 and 10.5. The presence of H-ions in three distinct affinity levels on the surface is indicated. The significance of these levels is brought out on a comparison of the amounts of acid neutralised at the three inflexion points. A particular specimen gave the acidity values (A.V) 3.2, 14.0 and 42.0 in m. e., per 100 g. of dry matter calculated respectively at the first, second and third inflexions. K ions to the extent of 14.0 m.e. were also displaced from 100 g. of the ground muscovite in preparing the hydrogen mica.

The observed agreement between the quantity of displaced K found in the HCl extract of the original ground material and the A.V. at the second inflexion of the resulting hydrogen mica shows that this inflexion marks the completion of the neutralisation of H-ions acquired by the surface of the platelets in exchange for their exposed potassium ions. Such H-ions are, of course, bonded to the surface by the negative charges arising from the isomorphous replacement of every fourth Si ion in the tetrahedral layer of the lattice by an Al ion.

The A. V.'s calculated at the third and second inflexions of the titration curve are as 3:1. This is consistent with the idealised formula, $\dot{H}(Al_2)(AlSi_3)O_{10}(OH)_2$, of hydrogen mica and with the assumption that for each H ion (marked with an asterisk in the formula) of the above category, the two OH groups, which are structurally identical, react with the base through hexagonal rings of oxygens at the third, or, final inflexion. The portion of the titration curve between the second and third inflexions thus corresponds to the neutralisation of H ions dissociated from these OH groups.

The significance of the first (weak) inflexion in the titration curve is not quite apparent on the basis of the chemical composition of muscovite and its atomic structure as deduced from X-ray analysis (Jackson *et al.*, *loc. cit.*). This inflexion appears to differentiate between the H ions acquired by the surface in exchange for the exposed potassiums and it seems to allocate them between two sub-levels of affinity on the surface. H ions at flake edges and corners would, of course, have bonding energies different from those on the cleavage planes. Other factors also require to be considered. They will be fully discussed elsewhere.

The observed weak acid character of hydrogen mica fails to confirm Pauling's prediction ("Nature of Chemical Bonds", Cornell University Press, Ithaca, 1939, p. 376) that it should behave as a very strong acid judged from his electrostatic valence rules as applied in this case to linked Si-O and Al-O tetrahedra. Apparently, factors not coming within the purview of these rules and not immediately deducible from them have to be considered. This will be done in a separate communication.

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